

Labour, Human Mobility, and Rights: The Role of the SDGs and the ILO

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INTRODUCTION

What has been happening globally over the years on labour migration issues has existed since the beginning of humanity, but is now increasing at a daily rate. Despite the benefits involved, some victims of migration do not have full, in-depth knowledge of the new environment, place of work, cultural diversity, and the laws that guide labour migration. Some smart companies hide certain facts for selfish gain through commercialization, underpayment, and violation of migrant labour rights, including many kinds of abuse.

Despite the benefits associated with labour migration such as enhancing economic growth, social activities, population growth, and development in the new environment both in business and in the country as a whole, there are still pressing concerns.

In the year 2020, when the epidemic happened globally, it led me to study some online courses with the United Nations. This really gave me insight into a broader view of what is happening and why there are great shifts in careers, development, economic situations, values, and hardship in underdeveloped, developing, and developed countries, including the Western world. The United Nations is doing great work in managing diversity in the midst of adversity caring for and providing for refugees, protecting migrants and human rights, and promoting the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) for 2030. These and many other factors will lead to increasing labour migration, which I will present in this article.

As long as there is no economic stability, no security, no political stability, high unemployment rates, abject poverty, unstable work, hunger, and a lack of good environments for work and social life there will always be increasing labour migration every day!

First of all, I want to thank the International Labour Organization (ILO) for the initiative to launch this annual Global Media Competition. It helps provide more insights, different views, and observations to deeply understand what is happening in labour migration, both nationally and internationally. This supports accurate reporting that helps make proper suggestions and recommendations to the United Nations for appropriate policies, procedures, and procurement being the only tripartite UN agency since 1919 that brings together governments, employers, and workers of its 187 member states.

This information will also help the International Labour Organization develop strategies, policies, and affirmative procedures to ensure labour migration is well-secured, advanced, and transparent for effective economic purposes built on trust. This will be a great help to the world generally.

In this article, I will be sharing some insights as a Certified Management Consultant and Certified Management Specialist. The information here will also contribute to the realization of some goals for which the International Labour Organization (ILO) was established.

The aim of the International Labour Organization (ILO) is to recognize fair and balanced reports that contribute to the elimination of xenophobia and discrimination against migrant workers;

- It also gives equal voice to workers, employers, and governments to ensure that the views of their social partners are clearly reflected in labour migration policies.
- It promotes rights at work.
- It encourages decent employment for both women and men opportunities for all.
- It promotes labour standards, the development of policies, and the creation of programs that foster equality.
- It enhances social protection and strengthens dialogue on work-related issues.

International Labour Organization partners include:

The International Trade Union Confederation

The International Organisation of Employers

The Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights

The International Federation of Journalists

Human Rights Watch

Equal Times

Solidarity Center

Migrants Forum in Asia

The European Union - Funded Project

Global Action to Improve the Recruitment Framework of Labour Migration (2017–2022)

The Swiss Agency for Development and Cooperation (SDC)–Funded Project

Integrated Program on Fair Recruitment Phase 1 (2015–2018), Phase 2 (2018–2022),
Phase 3 (2022–2025)

Definition of Key Terms

"Labour Migration"

What is Labour?

Labour can be used as a noun or a verb.

As a **noun**, labour means employment, work, etc.

As a **verb**, it means hard work or making great effort to achieve a particular goal or target.

Of course, the two uses may be interchangeable depending on context.

There are many types of labour or, to put it more clearly, types of labourers. These include:

- Skilled Labour
- Unskilled Labour
- Semi-Skilled Labour
- Professional Labour
- Manual Labour

These are human resources responsible for the production of goods and services. Labour is a major factor of production that coordinates other factors to ensure an organization functions properly and achieves its goals. Therefore, labour is a fundamental and active factor of production due to its contribution and coordination in the production of commodities and services.

What is Migration?

Migration is the movement of people from one place to another either within a state, across countries, or between continents. This movement can be due to many factors, including economic instability, financial hardship, war, life values, climate conditions, natural disasters, career development, or the need for survival.

Labour Migration refers to the movement of workers skilled, unskilled, semi-skilled, professionals, manual labourers, etc. to other parts of the state, country, or continent for employment. This is a major shift influenced by many factors, which I will write about in this article, based on my experience as a Management Consultant and Human Resources

Management Trainer. I will explore various views, advantages, disadvantages, risks, and irregularities involved.

Types of Labour Migration:

- **Internal Labour Migration** – Movement within the state, often within one's region of residence.
- **External Labour Migration** – Movement across states, countries, or continents for work.
- **Emigration of Labour** – Temporary relocation en route to a final workplace or employment destination (like a stopover).
- **Immigration of Labour** – Full relocation to a new country or environment for employment.
- **Return Migration** – Workers returning to a place where they had lived or worked before.
- **Seasonal Labour Migration** – Movement based on seasonal jobs (e.g., during economic booms, climate demands, or winter shortages).
- **Domestic Labour Migration** – Workers, often women and children, employed for housework, many of whom face abuse and have their passports seized. In many cases, their wages go to someone else who arranged their travel.
- **Professional Labour Migration** – Professionals who are educated, informed, and aware of their rights and terms before migrating. This form of migration is typically better structured and more secure.

Labour migration is defined as the movement of persons from their home state to another state or country for the purpose of employment. Today, an estimated 86 million persons are working in a country other than their country of birth, according to the International Organization for Migration (IOM).

The number of labour migrants will continue to increase due to various reasons both positive and negative. These reasons impact both their country of origin and the new country or state where they are employed.

THE HISTORY OF LABOUR MIGRATION

The history of labour is as old as the world. Over the years, people have looked for safe places, conducive environments, pasture, food, survival, security, values, etc. This has led to the movement or migration of labour from place to place within regions, countries, and continents.

No matter the level of awareness and resources a country has, if they are not well managed and administered properly for effective economic growth and political stability, there will be greater shifts in migration of people, labour, and businesses.

People must survive, and they explore different means especially legal ones to become equipped, empowered, and fulfilled in life so they can secure their families economically. All of these depend on what individuals value in life desires, wants, growth, development, secure benefits, etc. These are the true factors leading to the increasing rate of labour migration in today's world.

Solutions and Suggestions

In view of this, each government of any nation must endeavour to maintain economic stability, security, and political stability, and refrain from chaos, protests, and war. The government must be sensitive to the needs of its citizens and consult stakeholders before making policies and laws. This will help such policies to be effective in practice without causing unrest in the country.

This will also help balance labour migration so that there won't be serious labour shortages in any sector when workers migrate to places they consider better for their lives. After all, it's a free world.

THE HISTORY OF HUMANITY IN MIGRATION

In the history of humanity, migration has always existed driven by the desire for a better quality of life and secure job opportunities with long-term benefits and leverage. This continuous trend is why international labour migration strategies, in line with the 1919 agreement with the United Nations, were developed. These strategies include positive suggestions, ethical principles, and

honest reporting designed to be analysed and implemented as policies across the 187 member states of the United Nations.

The aim is to ensure fair provisions ranging from basic salary to allowances and other benefits and to prevent abuse of labour migration, such as using it as a cover for child trafficking, commercial prostitution, slavery, exploitation, abuse of rights, or the sale of organs like kidneys under false employment claims in another country, often without the person's consent.

The Fear, the Risk, and the Irregularities

These abuses in labour migration make workers skeptical, fearful, and doubtful of the potential benefits which could have helped both the labour migration companies and the receiving countries enjoy mutual economic growth and sustainable development.

For genuine labour migration to happen, employment must follow standard recruiting procedures approved by the government of the originating country. The labour migration agency must provide clear information about the place of work and residence. Much work is still needed in this area, especially in developing nations and even in some developed ones.

The recruitment and procurement of labour whether skilled, unskilled, semi-skilled, manual, or professional must be legally backed and transparent. Workers must give full, informed consent and understand the terms and conditions of their employment before embarking on the migration journey.

BACKGROUND CHECKS FOR RECRUITING

Background checks should be conducted both by the recruiters and the employers in the destination country for security, values, and authenticity. Employment details must be clearly stated and made public, considering the change in environment. Without proper supervision by the government, its agencies, or the embassy, there's a high risk of human rights violations. This

is why the government or embassy must be aware of and involved in the labour migration process.

The Irony of Citizen and Government

However, some governments may not want their citizens especially labourers to leave their country permanently. This is especially the case when migration trends rise sharply. But when people see their lives wasting away while their counterparts in other countries enjoy better living conditions, they will find every possible means to leave. If the government blocks labour migration, it can be seen as a violation of human rights.

The Challenge to Every Nation

This is a serious challenge for every responsible nation: to care for its citizens and its labour force, providing benefits that encourage them to stay. The environment should be able to compete with the destination countries in terms of opportunities, comfort, and development.

When there is political stability, economic growth, societal values, security, and access to basic amenities, labour migration will reduce because no one wants to leave their home when it is safe, comfortable, and promising.

I think it's high time the United Nations Assembly addressed this issue. Any president who does not uphold the laws of fair employment and labour rights should be seen as violating human rights and should be held accountable. The standard of living in every country must be a top priority. The denial of human rights, quality of life, and decent work conditions has serious effects on labour migration.

INTERNATIONAL LABOUR ORGANIZATION (ILO)

In meeting up with the declaration on the agenda of the United Nations towards 2030 for the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the International Labour Organization must play a vital role. When labour and job employment are secure and well-paid with full benefits, a single mother will be able to send her children to school and to any level of education. Working parents will have access to benefits. The Sustainable Development Goals will be actualized by 2030 if not all, then at least part especially in relation to labour migration, employment, and settlement for a decent standard of living.

Now, due to the lack of a proper environment and adequate benefits, we have increasing labour migration. This is separate from expatriates, consultants, international companies, trainers, etc., who enter countries to fulfill their assignments and return home afterward.

However, if the environment is not conducive, secure, stable, and comfortable, the next logical action is to look for employment that can take care of all responsibilities and ensure economic stability under any circumstance.

Do you know that the pandemic in 2020 caused many workers to rethink where to live, where to stay, and what kind of job would offer security in case another lockdown were to occur?

Where will I stay to be safe with my family? Where will my health be properly cared for? These are the daily thoughts of responsible workers after the lockdown. So, greater shifts and migration are happening between jobs, locations, and countries. Labour migration is increasing daily because people want to survive.

Survival is the first thing that comes to mind. As a responsible person, you cannot abandon your family while you enjoy a better life in another country. So, many labour migrants will eventually take their families with them. If not immediately, then after some years. This is the reality of life!

BENEFITS OF WELL-GOVERNED AND SAFE LABOUR MIGRATION

The benefits of well-organized, governed, and legalized safe labour migration are numerous. They help humanity and society both in the countries where workers reside and in their countries of origin. These benefits have helped millions of people home and abroad to enjoy hope, comfort, education, healthcare, and access to social amenities, among others.

In fact, the inflow or transfer of money through banks to meet domestic needs in different countries and continents gives a glimpse into the benefits of well-governed and safe labour migration.

Some of the benefits include:

- Labour migration improves economic growth for any nation.
- It serves as a passion and a path for career development.
- Labour migration helps with business expansion.
- It enhances security by minimizing company losses and promoting economic stability.
- It brings fulfilment to labourers and their dependants.
- It offers exposure, enlightenment, and encouragement.
- It promotes cultural methods that strengthen family values.
- It provides opportunities to learn other cultures, lifestyles, and adaptation techniques.
- It helps solve the problem of labour shortages.
- It meets value-based needs in various ways.
- It builds trust, stability, and compensation systems.
- It provides secured healthcare and insurance.
- It offers future security both in work and in life.
- It strengthens currency value and international exchange rates.
- It fosters good policy and governance through effective policymakers.
- It supports favourable labour laws for both migrants and employers
- It upholds work ethical standards through the efforts of the International Labour Organization.
- It encourages fair recruitment without bias or racism.

THE RISKS AND DANGERS OF IRREGULAR, UNSAFE, AND POORLY GOVERNED LABOUR MIGRATION

When proper measures are not put in place by national and international authorities, the result is numerous risks for labour migration. Therefore, it is essential to implement precautions, raise awareness, and adopt sound immigration policies and labour standards.

Problems that arise when appropriate measures are not implemented include:

- Illegal labour migration that results in human trafficking.
- Labour migration for commercial abuse, such as child exploitation in domestic work.
- Political instability when terrorists disguise as labour migrants.
- Poor working conditions unexpected realities of new workplaces and environments.
- Unfavourable policies when migrants are unaware of full employment terms.
- Policy-making without stakeholder consultation leading to protests and reduced productivity.
- Lack of government sensitivity causing inflation and worsening economic conditions.
- Overpopulation of labour in the marketplace exceeding job demand in some regions.
- Natural disasters, chaos, protests, and war the unpredictability of new environments.
- Labour shortages due to mass migration or pandemics.
- Work overload migrants may be exploited and overused.
- Economic hardship, inflation, and abject poverty.
- Value systems migration reflects what people desire and value in life.
- Cultural transfer migrants bring their cultures and behaviours into new environments.
- Abuse and violation of human rights.
- Exposure to illegal employment due to unfamiliar surroundings.
- Lack of clarity risks like organ trafficking disguised as employment.
- Poor recruitment practices risking the employment of terrorists as labour migrants.
- Abuse of women employed as domestic workers.
- Underpayment and exploitation.

THE LABOUR MIGRANTS CONTRIBUTE A LOT TO SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT AND THE ECONOMY

- They fill the labour shortage gap.
- The labour tax helps development and infrastructure.
- The labour migrants contribute to social life.
- They help production targets to be met.
- The workers enhance the employers' achievements.
- Labour migration empowers their family members in their home country.
- The labour boosts markets, services, and society growth.
- They help population growth and advancement.
- Labour migration helps the economy to grow and be stable.
- Labour migration enhances the quality standard of living.

CONCLUSION

Labour migration has truly helped the development of both countries because most of the workers, after paying their taxes to the country they work in, also send money back to their home countries or where they migrated from for their families, friends, and for building properties for their old age.

Despite the irregularities and risks involved caused by some bad people who commercialize abuses of various kinds, such as paying less, child slavery, women being forced to do things against their will, prostitution disguised as employment, and oppression the benefits still fulfill good purposes. The advantages far outweigh the cons.

Therefore, the International Labour Organization (ILO) must engage, collaborate, and conduct thorough investigations within each country among the United Nations member states to identify and remove the bad eggs.

Labour migration should be encouraged. I have observed that many exposed individuals in developing nations once lived and worked in developed countries before returning to their home country to become Mayors, Governors, Businesswomen, Businessmen, etc. They, in return, integrate what they have learned, studied, and experienced, implementing structural developments based on the places they worked as migrants.

Thus, labour migrants reinvest in their homeland through infrastructure, businesses, and political initiatives aimed at progress. This has helped society and humanity to develop and make positive economic impacts.

We Need Ourselves in the Ecological System!

The community is transformed; they are respected and admired. To be honest with you, this has led to greater leverage for the Third World. Moreover, in the Western world, economic growth has also been boosted.

This ecological system is showing us that we need each other whether in developing or developed countries. We are useful to one another. Therefore, labour migration should be encouraged, while the risks involved must be eliminated and discouraged for better productivity.

The world is changing rapidly, and it is necessary to take more drastic steps to stop the activities that have become a threat to labour migration.

Lastly, this annual competition will help discover new ideas, insights, thoughts, etc., that will enhance and support the International Labour Organization in gathering information in an organized and knowledgeable way. This will lead to better policy formulation for the United Nations General Assembly to consider for the improvement of today's world.

It will complement the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by 2030. Labour migration is a reality of what is happening, and we must be proactive because it is helping humanity at large.